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Research Article

**EVALUATION OF FETAL (MCA) VERSUS (UA) COLOR
DOPPLER ULTRASOUND FOR DETERMINING NEWBORN
OUTCOME IN OBSTRUCTED GESTATIONAL WITH (FGR)****Muhammad Nauraiz Zubair, Dr. Muhammad Ibrahim Shahzad,
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Article Received: February 2020**Accepted:** March 2020**Published:** April 2020**Abstract:**

Purpose: The aim of the present study was to compare alterations in the fetal MCA versus umbilical artery (UA) pulsatility indices (PI) in complicated pregnancies by fetal growth restriction (FGR).

Place and Duration: In the Obstetrics and gynecology department Unit II of Services Hospital Lahore for one-year duration from May 2018 to April 2019.

Methods: One hundred and fifty pregnant women in the third quarter he participated in the study with FGR forecast. Tran's abdominal ultrasound was done to determine the weight of the fetus. After birth, all newborns were divided into 2 groups: Small for gestational age (SGA), not for SGA. We compare UA and MCA Doppler values in the SGA forecast. Data were evaluated by t-test and chi-square test.

Results: After the delivery, 126 Mothers had SGA and 24 subjects had newborns without SGA. Unlike UA PI, MCA artery PI, The SGA and non-SGA groups were significantly different ($p = 0.062$ for UA PI comparison; $p = 0.0001$ MCA PI for comparison). 40.5% reduction in fetuses in MCA IP from 126 cases UA PI increased in 22.2% of fetuses. There were significant differences in both specificity and sensitivity. Specificity towards UA PI for MCA PI ($p = 0.014$ for sensitivity; $p = 0.009$ for specificity).

Conclusion:

The results indicate that in all cases SGA decreased MCA PI, UA PI. Sensitivity, specificity and SGA prognosis for MCA PI was higher than UA PI.

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INTRODUCTION:

Fetal Growth Restriction (FGR) is well-defined as the inability to perform specific biometric measurements of the fetus or estimated weight for a given gestational age (less than the tenth percentile)¹. Responsible for FGR for various prenatal and postnatal types of morbidity and mortality². FGR incidence it is reported to be around 3-10%. It is divided into 2 groups by start time: early (Before 32 weeks) and late onset (after 32 weeks). Some of the factors causing FGR include motherhood³. Causes (hypertension, diabetes, cardiopulmonary diseases, anemia, malnutrition, smoking, drugs use), fetal causes (aneuploidy, congenital malformations, genetic diseases, including fetal infection, multiple pregnancy) and placental causes (placental insufficiency, placental infarction, placenta mosaic).

In the past, FGR fetal assessment was performed by electronic fetal monitoring and biophysical profile⁴. These methods have several disadvantages, including false positives. Findings leading to loss of time. Today Doppler speed measurement is a clinical tool was developed to assess blood flow and uteroplacental resistance in complex situations preeclampsia or FGR⁵.

Some studies have shown that the diagnosis and treatment of FGR depends on the umbilical cord. Arterial Doppler (UAD) and others have demonstrated the advantages of assessing uterine doppler artery^{6, 7}. The value of the combination of pulsation index (PI) of both uterine arteries to improve the umbilical artery (UA) and predict FGR, on the other hand, some studies have shown that there is no correlation. Relationship between fetal Doppler indices and predictive value for low gestational age (SGA).

The middle cerebral artery (MCA) can also predict the effect of brain disorders on the fetus, blood flow and direction. However, this parameter may change during the threat conditions such as placental insufficiency and hypoxemia due to stimulation of chemoreceptors and changes in vasodilators or vasoconstrictors⁸. MCA Doppler measurement was performed. It is recommended as an effective method of detecting fetal hypoxia causing perinatal side effects.

SGA estimation is valuable due to the possibility of early prevention and better treatment result. The purpose of this study was to compare UA and MCA Doppler values. FGR prediction of late onset for potential modification of obstetrics management.

METHODS:**Study population and study design**

This cohort study was conducted at the Obstetrics and gynecology department Unit II of Services Hospital Lahore for one-year duration from May 2018 to May 2019. Target group for pregnant women Third trimester of pregnancy with fetal FGR assessment by ultrasound. Admission Criteria. fetal growth <10 for all fetuses of the same gestational age in this percentile, gestational age 32 + 0 to 39 + 6 weeks, no single pregnancy and serious fetal abnormalities. Exclusion the criteria include premature membrane rupture, post-pregnancy pregnancy, and maternal fall development of preeclampsia. All participants have given their written consent and accepted routine prenatal care and delivery at our center.

Transabdominal ultrasound was performed to determine fetal weight. Estimated weight was below the 10th percentile according to the Hadlock formula, Doppler ultrasound UA and MCA were performed. Ultrasound examination was performed by a qualified perinatologist using Doppler and high-resolution ultrasound (ACUSON) (blind for examination) Sequoia 512TM is manufactured at Siemens Healthcare GmbH, USA. AT.). UA PI at the 95th percentile an invalid range was found (values greater than 1.2). MCA PI measured 2 mm higher angle between the inner neck and Doppler beam and the vessel in the axial plane set to 0-30. MCA PI below the 5th percentile was accepted as an invalid range (values below 0.9).

Immediately after birth, 1-2 ml of neonatal blood for the determination of arterial blood gases. It was extracted from UA with a heparinized syringe, labeled and transferred to a laboratory. Everything According to the Hadlock formula, newborns were divided into 2 groups: SGA and non-SGA. Data were compared between two groups in relation to MCA and UAPI indicators. In the end we compare Doppler values of UA and MCA in SGA estimation. Also related Factors between the two groups were assessed.

Participant characteristics

Demographic characteristics of mothers and their newborns, mother's age, body mass index (BMI), gestational age, parity, style of delivery, underlying diseases, newborn's weight, sex, Apgar 5-minute result, blood gas (ABG) results, neonatal complications, hospital reason for hospitalization, admission days to the neonatal intensive care unit (ICU), UA PI and MCA PI. All information has been collected and recorded on checklists.

Ethical issues

All collected data was considered confidential. All participants signed informed consent. In addition, the right of participants to suspend the work process

is guaranteed. Ethical consent for the study was obtained from the Institutional Audit Commission

RESULTS:

One hundred and fifty pregnant women with estimated fetal FGR (based on ultrasound results) were included in the study. After delivery, 126 mothers (84%) had newborns with SGA, and 24 subjects (16%) had newborns without SGA. The mean age of the mother in the SGA group compared to the groups without SGA was 27.83 5.85 and 27.45 5.55, respectively. Independent T-test analysis did not differ significantly between the two groups in maternal age ($p = 0.51$). Neonatal mortality was not observed and ventilation was not required in the newborn.

Our results showed that caesarean section in the SGA group was significantly more common than in the group without SGA ($p = 0.00$). There was a significant relationship between primary maternal disease and neonatal SGA birth ($p = 0.01$). The average birth weight in the SGA group was significantly lower than in the non-SGA group, and most newborns in this group had a newborn baby weight below the 5th percentile for gestational age ($p = 0.00$). More newborns in the SGA group were hospitalized at the ICU and remained longer than newborns in the second group ($p = 0.04$). There was a significant difference between the two groups in terms of mean umbilical cord blood pH (in the SGA group, 7.22 0.048, in the non-SGA group; 7.26 0.032, $p = 0.00$). Detailed data on the subjects and their neonates are presented in Table 1.

When it comes to Doppler testing, IP MCA between SGA and non-SGA groups was significantly different. However, there was no significant difference in UA PI between the two groups ($p = 0.00$ vs. $p = 0.06$) (Table 1). Table 2 shows detailed data on MCA and UA indicators. A decrease in MCA IP was observed in 40.5% of the fetus from 126 cases, and an increase in IP in UA in 22.2% of fetuses. Abnormal PIs were detected in one of 2 arteries in 47 cases, and abnormalities in both arteries in 16 cases. In newborn SGA with abnormal PI (MCA or UA), the pH of umbilical cord blood was significantly lower than the pH of newborn SGA with normal PI (7.20 0.012 vs. 7.24 0.051, $p =$

0.01). On the other hand, in the non-SGA group, this relationship was not significant (in newborns with normal pH = normal PI = 7.25 0.044, blood pH normal PI = 7.26 0.028, $p = 0.26$).

In addition, the results of the study showed significant correlations between ICU hospitalization and abnormalities in both MCA and UA. In fact, 150 newborns had normal MCA PIs in 96 cases, and 9 of them had to be hospitalized in the ICU. Meanwhile, 54 newborns had abnormal MCA PI and 28 patients were hospitalized ($p = 0.00$). In addition, 21 of 116 newborns with normal IP AI were hospitalized and 34 had abnormal PI IP, of which 16 were hospitalized in the ICU ($p = 0.00$).

Detailed analysis also showed that 126 children with SGA were hospitalized in the ICU more often in infants with abnormal PI MCA than in children with normal PI MCA (54.9% vs. 9.3%, $p = 0.0001$). This positive correlation was also significant with normal UA PI for abnormal UA PI (57.1% vs. 19.4%, $p = 0.00$). On the other hand, the relationships between the same variables were not significant in newborns in the non-SGA group.

In addition, we found that the incidence of neonatal respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) was significantly higher in children with SGA with abnormal PI MCA ($p = 0.01$). On the other hand, when comparing IP with normal abnormal MCA, the RDS frequency was not different in infants without SGA. In addition, the RDS frequency between SGA (3.2%) and non-SGA (4.2%) groups was not different.

There was a significant correlation between the cerebral placental relationship (CPR) and MCA PI; however, this correlation was not observed for CPR and UA PI ($p = 0.00$ vs. $p = 0.95$, respectively). The results showed that $CPR < 1$ was a potential predictor of a negative result among infants with SGA (Table 3). Table 4 shows the sensitivity, specificity and predictive value for MCA PI and UA PI. There were significant differences in sensitivity and specificity between MCA PI and UA PI ($p = 0.01$; $p = 0.00$, respectively). The results of the study revealed a significantly lower value in SGA prediction for the UA PI index compared to MCA PI.

Table 1. Clinical characteristic data of subjects and their neonates

Variables	SGA group N=126	Non-SGA group N=24	P value
BMI	28.06±2.50	28.20±1.76	0.779+
Parity (n %)			
- Multipar	54 (42.86)	9 (37.5)	
- Nulipar	72 (57.14)	15 (62.5)	0.626 ++
Underlying complications			
- Pregnancy induced HTN	1	0	
- HTN	4	1	
- Gestational diabetes	3	1	
- Diabetes	4	0	0.014 +++
- Gestational age (wk ± SD))	38.01±1.24	38.21±1.08	0.497+
- Previous SGA	6	1	
Type of delivery			
- NVD	48 ((38.1)	16 (66.7)	
- C/S	78 (61.9)	8 (33.3)	0.009 ++
Neonatal SGA			
- <5th percentile	91 (72/22)	0	0.0001+++
- 5-10th percentile	35 (27.78)	0	
- >10th percentile	0	24 (100)	
Sex			
- Male	43	10	
- Female	83	14	0.0479++
5th minute apgar score<7	1 (.79)	0	0.693+++
Mean birth weight (g ± SD)	2171.23±452.16	3031±294.36	0.0001+
Days of admission	9.94±3.82	5.25±3.68	0.026+
NICU admission	35 (27.77)	2 (8.33)	0.043 +++
Umbilical PI	1.368±0.606	1.087±0.630	0.062+
Cord blood pH	7.22±0.048	7.26±0.032	0.0001+
Cerebral PI	1.409±0.377	1.799±0.412	0.000+1

+T student Test, ++Chi-squareTest, +++ Fisher Exact Test

Table 2. Both groups' pulsatility index value for UA and MCA

Pulsatility index	MCA	UA
Non-SGA group		
- Normal	21 (87.5)	18
- Increased	-	6
- Decreased	3 (12.5)	-
SGA group		
- Normal	75 (59)	98 (77.7)
- Increased	-	28 (22.2)
- Decreased	51 (40.5)	-

Table 3. Comparison of MCA- UA indices and Cerbroplacental Ratio

	UA PI	MCA PI	CPR
Non-SGA	1.787	1.799	1.145
SGA	1.768	1.409	0.901
P value+	0.953	0.0001	0.018

Table 4. Prediction value of UA, MCA and both MCA & UA for detecting abnormal fetal outcome

Doppler index	Sensitivity (%)	Specicity (%)	Prediction value(%)	
			Positive	Negative
UA	53	69	88	33
MCA	74	93	95	66
Both MCA & UA	64	81	91	41

DISCUSSION:

Although the use of UA Doppler ultrasound is a common method for assessing uteroplacental circulation and predicting negative perinatal results, recent studies have shown the importance of DCA Doppler for prenatal monitoring. This study compared changes in fetal MCA and UA PI in complex pregnancies (due to FGR). As far as we know, this study is one of the first studies focused on SGA predictive values for MCA and UA PI.

The most important finding of this study was 126 cases of SGA, with statistically a decrease in MCA PI statistically more pronounced than changes in UA PI (40.5% vs. 22.2%, respectively). According to our findings, other studies have also shown that diastolic blood flow (showing that blood is redistributed to important organs) appears earlier in the fetal cerebral circulation than the artery and UA aorta. In addition, changes in the cerebral circulation are more sensitive to changes in the systemic circulation that can predict the condition of the fetus. According to other studies, the results showed a significant risk of negative perinatal results due to FGR⁹. The frequency of cesarean section, low birth weight, prolonged hospitalization and acidosis were more common in newborns with SGA than in newborns without SGA¹⁰. Neonates with FGR had greater fetal death, neonatal death, and prematurity complications (such as neurocognitive delay, metabolic syndrome, and cardiovascular disease). Nanthakomon *et al*¹¹. It also turned out that children with ASG with abnormal IP PI had a high frequency of hospitalization and long-term ICU hospitalization. In addition, low birth weight, hospitalization in the intensive care unit, respirator demand and <7 Apgar score less than 5 minutes were common in children with SGA with abnormal MCAPI.

But; we could not find a correlation <7 in the 5th minute between the SGA result and the Apgar result. According to our findings, Nannig *et al*. In addition, 43 SGA showed low pH in newborns. Sharma *et al*¹² revealed the importance of maternal diseases such as mother's health, behavioral habits underlying mother's disease, and lack of coincidence between placental nutrient supply and fetal demand in FGR etiology. Werner *et al*. In 2885 children with SGA,

Caesarean delivery was more frequent than normal vaginal delivery (57.9% vs. 42.1%, $p < 0.05$).

Such widespread perinatal negative results indicate the importance of early SGA detection and intervention. According to our results, a significant correlation was observed between CPR and IP MCA. CPR <1 was found to be a potential negative predictor of outcomes in infants with SGA. The results also showed high sensitivity, specificity and predictive value of average brain IP (74%, 93% and 95%, respectively) in SGA prediction. Our discovery was consistent with other studies; Hemlata *et al*¹³. 71%, 92% and 94% showed that MCA represents sensitivity, specificity and a positive predictive value to detect abnormal fetal SGA-related results. Ibrahim *et al*. It also revealed a lower PI MCA value as a highly specific value for FGR prediction and fetal death. Monteith *et al*¹⁴. They showed the importance of an abnormal CPR series <1 as a potential predictor of adverse effects among 1116 fetuses of SGA. Finally, the results of this study showed false positive errors associated with ultrasound in the evaluation of fetal weight. Although 150 fetuses were diagnosed with FGR in the third trimester of pregnancy, 24 newborn babies had no SGA. According to our results, Williams *et al*¹⁵. He showed that fetal weight was about 20% of false positive and 20% of false negative results in ultrasound.

Our work contained some limitations. First, the data was limited to the third trimester of pregnancy. Secondly, we do not take into account other maternal variables that may affect outcomes such as ethnicity and smoking. Although it can provide informational data, uterine artery related indicators are not included. Finally, a larger sample size is needed to evaluate various factors.

CONCLUSION:

The results of our study showed that in SGA cases, the decrease in MCA PI was statistically more significant than changes in UA PI. MCA PI sensitivity, specificity and predictive values for SGA prediction were higher than for UA PI.

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